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WAYS TO ENSURE THE STABILITY OF STATE FINANCES BY INCREASING LOCAL BUDGET REVENUES

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Abstract. *In the article, on the example of the budget system of Uzbekistan, the ways of increasing the data of local budgets and thereby ensuring the stability of state finances are considered. proposals and recommendations have been formed.*

Keywords: *local budget, income, state finance, tax.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, one of the most important and urgent aspects of the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan is the large-scale institutional reforms in the economy, including the financial system, and in this regard, the formation of large-scale social cooperation between not only institutions and state agencies of the society, but also among different groups of the population and development.

The budget-tax system, in addition to being a financial policy aimed at a specific goal, redistributes a part of the gross national product and in this way directly participates in changing, diversifying and modernizing the structural structure of the economy, ensuring that it is focused on social protection of the population.

All expenses of the budget system are distributed among different budgets, which means that one or another expense is included in a specific budget. This is due, firstly, to the fact that the financed institution belongs to the republican and local bodies, and secondly, to the significance of the financed

expenditure.

Adoption and implementation of social programs in our republic, strengthening of the social policy aimed primarily at supporting the disadvantaged sections of the population, raising a healthy generation, increasing the well-being of the population increases the importance of the local budget.

Literature review

K.Kobulov et al. declares, local government bodies are interested in the flow of income to the local budget and targeted use of resources, because the rate of growth of the local economy and culture is directly related to the organization of work on the mobilization of local resources [1]. This, in turn, allows to ensure the successful implementation of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

N.V. Pokrovskaia and A.V. Belov in their research work, the tax revenue system of local authorities in Japan has a number of important features related to the complex configuration of centralization and decentralization, which took different forms at different stages of historical development [2].

Melnyk et al., and Vatamanyuk-Zelinska and Sytnik studies revealed negative trends in regional economies under the influence of quarantine measures introduced during the first wave of the COVID-19 epidemic [3-4]. Nevertheless, the development trends of regional economic systems during the coronavirus crisis require in-depth study, because they cannot be explained only by the laws and categories of economic theory.

Dzigbede et al. argue that local governments must collaborate for community benefits and that federal and state fiscal support is necessary for them, and it should consider and address fiscal disparities and social inequities with special attention paid to small local governments of limited capacity [5].

I.Jumaniyazov and V.Abdurayimov that local budgets are important in the implementation of national economic and social tasks, first of all, in the distribution of state funds and development of social infrastructure, they are the main financial source for the activities of local authorities, and in the implementation of the state's socio-economic policy on the ground they emphasize that it plays the main role [6].

According to Bazylevych and Balastryk, local budget revenues are formed from their own sources, and at the same time, state taxes, fees and other mandatory payments are attached [7].

Z.Abdullaev said that in the formation of the local budget's own income, the stability of the local budget's sources of income, improvement of taxation mechanisms, actions taking into account the perspectives of local authorities, the increase of local budget revenues, ensuring that local authorities stimulate the socio-economic development of the region are of great importance. admits [8].

Z. Ruziev states that local budget revenues and state budget expenditures are directed to the population living in the regions based on the distribution of the national income created in the country and to strengthening the revenue part of the local budgets delivering its results [9].

Analysis and results

Localization of economic and social processes has been observed in many countries in the world

whose economies have been transitioning to market relations in recent decades. The functions of managing these processes are being transferred from the central (federal) authority to regional state management bodies. Based on this factor, the areas of local finance are rapidly expanding. Therefore, the amount of local budgets has increased, and in many countries its share is a very large part of state budget resources.

Through local budgets, the state implements an active social policy in the country. At the present time, in many countries, all expenses related to public education, health care, public utility services, construction and maintenance of highways are covered by allocating the necessary funds to the budgets of these regional state authorities. fully funded. It should be noted that the range of activities financed through local budgets is constantly expanding. Currently, in many countries, local budgets support not only general education schools, but also institutions of higher and secondary special education, large health care facilities, law enforcement, internal security, environmental protection. and other activities are also being financed. It is worth noting that central and local government bodies use local budgets to equalize the level of economic and social development of different regions of the country (or reduce the difference). The main reason for this is that according to geographical, historical, demographic and a number of other factors, some regions of the country have advanced in economic and social development, while on the contrary, some regions have lagged behind in economic and social development.

Special regional programs are developed by the central government of the country in order to eliminate this negative situation or to reduce the difference as much as possible. The necessary funds for the implementation of this special program are allocated from the revenues of the local budgets of the relevant administrative-territorial units, as well as from the appropriate taxes of the higher level budgets (federal or republican budgets). In this case, in addition to allocating allocations from some federal taxes, subsidies are also given to the relevant regional budgets, that is, based on the developed program, for specific purposes (health care, education development, road construction, communal service facilities, etc.) financial resources are allocated from the federal (republic) budget. Economically developed countries that are members of the European Union allocate financial funds through special funds for the costs of retraining the unemployed in order to end unemployment in the new member countries (Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania).

In addition to the local taxes that fall to the local budgets, some state taxes were also attached to the Budget Code, that is, these taxes are not based on the regulations determined annually according to the current legislation, but directly to the local budgets. We believe that this factor will have a positive effect on increasing the income of local budgets in the finance and tax departments of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city.

Effective functioning and development of the regional economic system cannot be realized only through self-regulation mechanisms of the market. The role of the state is very important in this. On the basis of various economic supports, the state tries to eliminate disparities between regions and to ensure economic growth, employment and create the necessary infrastructure in them. It is most often used by the state to regulate the economy

one of the levers is the budget system.

With the development of the market economy, attention to local budgets is increasing in budgetary relations. The role of local budgets in the development of the regional economy is increasing. This can be seen from the activities financed and implemented by them. Measures of local importance are mainly financed from local budgets. In particular, in the organization of regional infrastructure, restoration of labor resources, social activities that serve to increase the labor welfare of the population are carried out. The financing of these activities on time and in the required amount will directly affect the improvement of the business environment in the regions and the development of the economy. Therefore, ensuring the stability of local budget revenues, their financial independence and solvency is a very important issue. According to Article 52 of the Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following are the sources of local budget revenues: receipts from state taxes, local taxes and other mandatory payments, non-refundable cash receipts from legal entities and individuals, as well as from foreign countries, markets income and other income.

Local budget revenues are not able to fully cover expenses. In order to cover these expenses, in order to eliminate the disparity between regions and prevent differentiation, the amount of norms allocated from state taxes will be increased, subsidies, subsidies and transferred revenues will be allocated by the republic budget. There are several downsides to this:

1. It leads to the loss of financial independence of local budgets whose costs are covered by grants and subsidies and increases their dependence on financial resources.

Creates a sense of self-sufficiency in local budgets living on subsidies and subsidies.

3. The withdrawal of excess revenues of donor budgets, whose revenues are higher than their costs, extinguishes their interest in further increasing the tax base and revenues.

In order to further develop the economy of the regions and fulfill the tasks assigned to them on time and in full, it is necessary to further increase the source of income of the local budgets. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the following directions:

- increasing the interest of local budgets in increasing the tax base:
- introduction of paid services to residents and businesses in the regions. For example, providing communal services. In developed countries, paid services provided to the public sector are one of the main sources of income for local budgets:
- giving local authorities the right to attract financial resources from domestic and foreign markets. Because this method is widely used in international practice, especially in economically developed countries.

To ensure the stability of state finances by increasing local budget revenues, it is important to improve the existing state finance system and study the factors of its development.

In the process of reforming the national economy, the impact of the reforms on the state economic policy is manifested not only in the liberalization of the economic policy, but also in taking into account the consequences of globalization for the institutional change of the financial system. Creating the institutional structure of the financial system that ensures the accuracy of financial flows is an important element of state policy.

It is an important condition for the functioning of the free financial market, which involves the reform of state finances, the use of certain information determined by the financial regulation and

control bodies.

Budgeting for efficiency is considered the next stage of the budgeting methods that are used in practice (expenditure planning), or budgeting per capita (since 2005), and it increases the control over the high efficiency of the expenses spent from the budget, the quality of budget services, its transparency and efficiency. At the same time, the harmonization of programmatic targeted result financing and medium-term budget policy is not only the mobilization of budget funds in the strategic directions of socio-economic development, the optimization of expenses depending on the goals and according to time, but also the efficiency of the state budget expenses. allows to increase.

Implementation of a financial audit system aimed at ensuring the implementation of normative legal acts in the field of budgetary relations and preventing actions to violate them, related to the relations of state financial resources. is an important institutional direction of improving the legislation on In this, it includes two directions - that is, internal audit and external audit. The current system of audit in the field of public finance is assigned to relevant bodies as an audit covering a certain period with existing regulatory legal documents.

Adherence to the requirements of financial audit legislation as a set of tools for orderly and effective management of assets and liabilities and liabilities of the state, including the budget, and activities related to budget funds; checking the reliability, accuracy and completeness of budget and accounting documents; prevent errors and misrepresentations; execution of orders and orders; ensuring the integrity of the property and strictly following the policy of the management; detection of extortion and errors; intended to facilitate the implementation of the objectives of timely preparation of reliable financial information. Despite the fact that there is currently an audit of the activities of economic entities in our republic, the state financial audit system requires further development from the point of view of legal documents, as well as the creation and improvement of the audit organization methodology. First of all, the development of the system is aimed at improving the mechanism of effective and practical influence on the implementation of state finances, the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and state target funds. Monitoring and control of the implementation of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan, state trust funds, economic enterprises established by the state or state-owned enterprises and local budgets carried out by them is not only related to the state and the purposeful use of state budget funds. , but covers their compliance with social norms, the effectiveness of spending and, first of all, the implementation of the program tasks of spending these funds.

Conclusion

It is necessary to implement the following directions of ensuring the uniformity and efficiency of state finances.

1. Determining the size and composition of the state's obligations to the population and the economy, taking into account the needs of the country's socio-economic development, the value of the effectiveness of the structural reforms being implemented.

2. Transition to a unified procedure for providing services to the state finances, to ensure full transparency of the budget system, to eliminate delays in the delivery of funds to the recipient, to put an

end to their purposeless use, and to increase the efficiency of inter-budgetary relations, and to increase the effectiveness of budget and extra-budgetary funds at all levels of government. transfer of income and expenditure accounts to the Treasury for servicing.

3. Among the financial factors in arranging the incomes and expenses of local budgets, there are opportunities to ensure a high level of income to local budgets due to the introduction of the procedure of centralized payment of taxes by the main enterprises and the increase of tax collection.

In general, it is desirable to strengthen the activity of local state authorities in deepening the reforms on the arrangement of revenues and expenses of local budgets.

4. The issue of arrangement of tax revenues and expenses of local budgets requires the measures of determining the amount of local taxes, increasing the rates of some taxes, improving the practice of taxation and applying reducing coefficients in the tax system.

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